

Deploying Geomarketing in Advanced Industrial Decision-Making

Field Evidence from the Saudi Ceramics Manufacturing Sector

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Abstract

Decision-making processes in the industrial and commercial sectors—particularly in the ceramic industry, which is the focus of this study in Saudi Arabia—often rely on routine decisions, with geospatial data rarely taken into consideration. According to the author's studies, Riyadh accounted for approximately 37% of total projects (based on 2018 data, as shown in (Table 12), a figure that is also reflected in the size of the ceramic market. In 2025, urban development activity increased, driven by several large-scale projects, including the SEDRA project, which includes the construction of 30,000 villas.

This study aims to develop a quantitative model linking Geomarketing to competitive advantage, and to outline a roadmap for the geographical and financial factors that will determine future demand in the ceramic sector.

To achieve this, a sample of 120 senior managers and specialists from ceramic factories across all regions of the Kingdom was used. The analysis included confirmatory reliability tests, validity assessments, hierarchical multiple regression, and comprehensive diagnostic checks.

The Ceramic Geographic Sector Efficiency Index (CGSEI) is based on these inputs and provides a replicable, city-level metric to measure location attractiveness. It also incorporates three projected market scenarios through 2035, based on housing plans under Vision 2030.

Keywords: Geomarketing; geographic information systems; industrial decision-making; ceramics manufacturing; competitive advantage; supply chain efficiency; CGSEI index; Saudi Arabia.

1. Introduction

1.1 Problem statement

Urban activity in Saudi Arabia is on the rise and is closely linked to a set of major events "most notably Expo 2030 and the 2034 FIFA World Cup". These developments are driven by Vision 2030 and are expected to reshape demand for ceramic products. This transformation goes beyond previous temporal patterns; as ceramic manufacturers have largely relied on demographic data dating back to pre-2020 periods.

Currently, demand is shifting toward NEOM, westward to the new tourism destinations along the Red Sea, and toward central regions of the Kingdom, where urban expansion and projects supported by the Real Estate Development Fund are accelerating.

Geomarketing offers a structured analytical response to this evolving landscape. Unlike traditional statistical analyses, which treat demand merely as a numerical value, Geomarketing analyzes demand across both spatial and temporal dimensions. It reveals

not only the market demand size but also identifies high-demand locations, evaluates accessibility from various production sites, and assesses the associated logistical costs. Although the benefits of this approach have been widely documented across sectors such as retail, food manufacturing, and petrochemical distribution, its application in the Gulf region's ceramic industry remains limited. This gap represents a key motivation for the present study.

1.2 Research Problem

This study seeks to answer the following research question:

To what extent do Geomarketing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), when used as decision-making tools rather than merely technical applications, effectively contribute to achieving competitive advantage for ceramics manufacturers in Saudi Arabia through improved location selection and enhanced supply chain efficiency?

To address this main question, the study is structured around four key sub-questions:

1. To what extent is GIS-integrated Geomarketing adopted in ceramics companies, and what role does it play in decision-making processes?
2. Do Geomarketing data, location selection accuracy, and supply chain efficiency contribute to achieving competitive advantage?
3. What is the relative weight of each of these variables, and which pathway exerts the greatest practical impact?
4. How is demand for ceramic products geographically distributed across Saudi regions, and how is this distribution expected to evolve through 2035 under different growth scenarios?

In this context, it is important to highlight the role of GIS in supporting optimal site selection across both industrial and service sectors. GIS enables more informed decisions through the analysis of spatial data, helping organizations identify the most suitable locations based on multiple criteria (S. Ettazarini).

The importance of GIS is also evident in applications such as selecting appropriate sites for dam construction, where factors like soil type, surface water flow, and other environmental variables must be carefully evaluated.

Similarly, GIS supports the selection of optimal locations for new industrial plants by considering factors such as transportation costs, proximity to raw material sources, and closeness to high-demand markets (A. Bouzidi).

In this regard, a study by Han et al. (2020) examined multi-criteria decision-making approaches, particularly in the context of renewable energy project site selection. The study outlined various decision-making methodologies in this field, providing valuable insights for evaluating and selecting optimal locations for renewable energy facilities, and contributing to the sustainability and development of the renewable energy sector (HanZ.SunJ.XiaoC.ZhangS.ZhaoY).

1.3 Theories

This study is grounded in three main theoretical frameworks:

1. Information-Based Decision-Making Theory, which links the value of data and information to the quality of resulting decisions.
2. Resource-Based View (RBV), which assumes that Geographic Information Systems (GIS) constitute a valuable and difficult-to-imitate resource.
3. Transaction Cost Theory, which associates geographic location with cost structures.

Based on the above, the following hypotheses were tested:

- I. The quality of Geomarketing decisions has a positive effect on competitive advantage.
- II. The accuracy of site selection has a positive effect on competitive advantage.
- III. The use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has a positive effect on the quality of Geomarketing decisions.
- IV. The efficiency of supply chains is positively associated with competitive advantage.

1.4 Study Objectives

This study aims to achieve four main objectives:

1. To develop and validate a quantitative model linking competitive advantage with Geomarketing in the ceramic industry in Saudi Arabia.
2. To introduce the Ceramic Geographic Sector Efficiency Index (CGSEI) as a metric for comparing the efficiency of using geospatial data within the industry.
3. To conduct a market analysis using Geomarketing data, highlighting demand patterns, industrial infrastructure, and supply chain costs, along with forecasting demand through 2035.
4. To provide practical recommendations for decision-makers and researchers.

Theoretical Contribution

From a theoretical perspective, this study contributes to addressing the “transformation gap” highlighted in a study published in the journal *sciencedirect* (Pawinee Iamtrakul). It emphasizes the limited application of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in strategic decision-making across sectors in Saudi Arabia and the broader Gulf region.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Geomarketing: Conceptual Boundaries and Evolution

The concept of geomarketing emerged in the commercial field during the late 1980s, when what can be described as “spatial market analysis” began to take shape. It was initially adopted by large retail chains and refers to the use of commercial data integrated with geographically referenced demographic data to improve the quality of strategic decision-making.

Geographic Information Systems (GIS), however, differ from geomarketing. GIS represents the computational platform through which data are stored and processed, while its outputs are transformed into geomarketing insights that support decision-making processes.

This concept has evolved through three main phases:

- **Phase One (1985–2000):** Originated in the retail sector, focusing on identifying catchment areas and understanding the impact of geography on customer movement.
- **Phase Two (2001–2015):** Expanded to include market and competitive analysis, demographic targeting, and optimization of supporting functions such as logistics, alongside the increasing adoption of GIS software.
- **Phase Three (2015–Present):** Characterized by the emergence of big data, satellite-derived land-use indicators, and advanced demand forecasting techniques.

The current study focuses on the intersection between the second and third phases, particularly within an industrial sector that still largely relies on practices associated with the second phase.

Accordingly, the use of geomarketing in retail sales has evolved in parallel with advancements in GIS and its integration with artificial intelligence. Consumers increasingly prefer accessibility and proximity to retail locations, while manufacturers and traders seek to understand demographic distribution patterns (Ouyang & Luo, 2022).

Furthermore, successive industrial revolutions—especially the Fourth Industrial Revolution (2010–2020)—have accelerated the adoption of artificial intelligence, enhancing supply chain efficiency and strengthening the role of geomarketing in strategic and operational decision-making (Groumpos, 2021).

2.2 Methodological Literature Review: Approach and Findings

To ensure the existence of relevant prior studies, a systematic review was conducted following the PRISMA protocol, covering the Scopus and Web of Science databases for

the period from 2015 to 2025. The search strategy employed combinations of the following keywords:

(Geomarketing, geospatial analysis, GIS decision-making, and manufacturing, ceramics, industrial location, supply chain)

The findings of this review reveal a clear research gap: there is a lack of studies that integrate rigorous field-based measurement with spatial market analysis within the ceramic manufacturing sector in the Gulf region.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

From a theoretical perspective, this study posits that the adoption of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) acts as an enabling capability that operates through enhancing the quality of Geomarketing decisions, ultimately leading to improved competitive outcomes. This perspective reflects the core premise of the Resource-Based View (RBV), which emphasizes not merely the possession of resources, but the effective deployment of capabilities. In this context, the use of GIS alone does not automatically enhance spatial marketing capabilities; rather, it requires complementary capabilities - such as organizational efficiency - that enable the effective use of spatial data within the appropriate context and its transformation into sound decisions related to site selection and production allocation.

Within the proposed model, site selection and supply chain performance are incorporated as independent pathways alongside the quality of Geomarketing decisions. This is intended to emphasize that some competitive effects attributed to Geomarketing may, in fact, be realized through strategic decisions, rather than solely through ongoing tactical decisions. This structural distinction is precisely what hierarchical regression analysis allows to be decomposed and examined with clarity.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

A positivist stance was adopted for this study, operationalized through a cross-sectional survey design. This approach is well-suited to our objective of testing pre-defined hypotheses regarding the relationships between measurable variables within a limited organizational population.

Although the cross-sectional nature of the survey constrains the ability to infer causality in a strict temporal sense, our inferences about the directionality of relationships rely on well-established conceptual models rather than solely on assumptions derived from statistical analyses.

3.2 Population and Sample

A survey was conducted among specialists and managers in the ceramic sector across factories in Saudi Arabia, distributed within three main industrial regions. Using a **purposive layered sampling** approach to ensure appropriate representation, the final sample size reached **120 participants**, distributed as follows:

- **Eastern Region:** 52 participants
- **Riyadh Region:** 41 participants
- **Western Region:** 27 participants

This sample distribution reflects the actual concentration of expertise within the ceramic industry across the Kingdom.

Demographic Variable	Category	n (%)	Description
Gender	Male / Female	98 (81.7%) / 22 (18.3%)	Male-dominated sector
Age	30-39 / 40-49	42 (35.0%) / 38 (31.7%)	Mid-career majority
Education	Bachelor's / Master's	51 (42.5%) / 49 (40.8%)	University-educated sample
Experience	5-10 years / 11-15 years	38 (31.7%) / 34 (28.3%)	Substantial sector experience
Region	Eastern / Riyadh / Western	52 (43.3%) / 41 (34.2%) / 27 (22.5%)	Geographic distribution

Table 1. Sample Demographic Characteristics (n = 120)

3.3 Measurement Instrument

The questionnaire was developed through five sequential stages, resulting in a final instrument consisting of 22 items, measured باستخدام a five-point Likert scale (where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree).

The instrument comprises five main constructs:

- Use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (5 items)
- Effectiveness of Geomarketing Decisions (5 items)
- Site Selection (4 items)
- Supply Chain Efficiency (4 items)

- Competitive Advantage (4 items)

In line with a study by (Mohammed Aslam (2019)), the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was applied to verify the normality of data distribution as part of the statistical analysis. The results indicated that all scales demonstrated a high level of internal consistency reliability, both in the pilot study and in the final application.

4. Geo-Spatial Market Analysis of the Saudi Ceramics Industry

4.1 Market Size and Structural Composition

4.1.1 Market Trajectory 2019–2024

A notable growth has been observed in the Saudi market as a result of post-COVID-19 recovery, supported by renewed government spending on construction projects. The size of the ceramic market reached USD 3.7 billion in 2024, according to data from Mordor Intelligence.

On the other hand, a 2024 report by IndexBox indicates that pottery production in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, including Saudi Arabia, declined to 37,000 tons in 2024, representing a 13.6% decrease compared to 2023.

Year	Total Market (SAR B)	Local Production (SAR B)	Imports (SAR B)	Local Share %
2019	9.2	5.8	3.4	63%
2020	8.1	5.1	3.0	63%
2021	9.8	6.3	3.5	64.3%
2022	11.4	7.6	3.8	66.7%
2023	12.7	8.5	4.2	66.9%

2024	13.9	9.4	4.5	67.6%
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Table 2. Saudi Ceramics Market Development 2019–2024

Figure (4): Heat Map of Total and Per Capita Demand for Ceramics Across Regions | Source: Ministry of Municipal Affairs (2024) · General Authority for Statistics (2022)

4.1.2 Analysis of Secondary Ceramic Sectors

The ceramic industry cannot be treated as a single homogeneous sector, as this would fail to reflect its true structure and would obscure existing variations. In reality, the industry consists of five distinct sub-sectors that differ not only in size and growth rates, but also in:

- Geographic distribution of demand
- Proximity to raw material sources
- Price sensitivity based on demographic distribution

All of these factors play a critical role in shaping decisions related to factory location selection.

It is important to highlight that decorative tiles, despite representing a relatively small share—approximately 6% of the total ceramic market—exhibit the highest annual growth rate (9.8%). This segment is expected to capture a significant portion of the additional demand generated by projects led by the General Entertainment Authority under Vision 2030.

Sub-Segment	Market Share %	Growth %	Avg Price
Floor tiles	38.5%	8.2%	SAR 85/m ²
Wall tiles	26%	7.4%	SAR 72/m ²
Sanitary ware	19.5%	6.9%	Unit-based
Industrial ceramics	10%	5.1%	SAR 310
Decorative tiles	6%	9.8%	SAR 145/m ²

Table 3. Market Sub-Segment Structure, 2024

4.2 Population Density and Spatial Demand Generation

4.2.1 Population Distribution as a Tool for Industrial Decision-Making

Population distribution in Saudi Arabia shows that approximately 85% of the population is concentrated in eight main regions, which in turn reflects a strong concentration of ceramic demand in these areas.

For ceramic producers, this represents significant demand clusters, where—at least theoretically—the top three high-demand regions can be served from a single strategically located factory within less than 24 Hours.

However, population size alone is an insufficient indicator of actual demand.

According to reports by Mordor Intelligence, the Eastern Region is experiencing the fastest growth in demand for ceramic tiles, with an annual growth rate of **7.52%**.

This growth is driven by the expansion of industrial complexes and major projects—particularly petrochemical developments in Jubail and mining areas—which increase demand for factory flooring as well as worker housing.

Moreover, studies indicate that per capita ceramic consumption in the Eastern Region exceeds that of Riyadh, highlighting the importance of considering industrial activity and usage patterns—not just population size—when assessing market demand.

Region	Population (M)	Annual Demand (M m ²)	Per-Capita	Construction Projects
Riyadh	9	5.8	0.644	412
Eastern	5.4	3.9	0.722	289
Makkah	9.1	4.1	0.451	375
Madinah	2.2	1.4	0.636	124
Qassim	1.4	0.9	0.643	78
Other Regions	7.5	2.2	0.293	210

Table 4. Regional Ceramics Demand Distribution, 2024

Figure (2): Distribution of Population Density and Purchasing Power in Major Cities | Source: Population Census 2022 (General Authority for Statistics) · Ministry of Municipal Affairs (2024)

4.3 Transport Infrastructure: The Hidden Geography of Costs

4.3.1 Traditional Site Selection Mechanism

In general, when selecting a site for a ceramic factory, infrastructure analysis typically focuses on two main questions:

1. Accessibility: Is the site easily reachable?

2. Geographic Impact on Costs: How does the location affect shipping costs, and do differences between sites influence competitive positioning?

A report by Argaam highlights the significant impact of cost advantages on profitability. For example, Saudi Ceramics Company achieved a net profit of SAR 180.7 million in 2025, underscoring how factors such as regional shipping cost differences can strongly affect overall profitability and factory operational strategy.

Logistics Corridor	Length (km)	Capacity (t/day)
(Riyadh–Dammam)	404	48,000
Makkah–Riyadh Expressway	989	35,000
Eastern Gulf Coastal Road	512	42,000
Jeddah–Madinah Highway	421	28,000

Table 5. Strategic Logistics Corridors for Ceramics Freight

Figure (3): Transportation Network and Logistics Corridors for Ceramic Freight — Costs and Efficiency | Source: Saudi Land Transport Federation (2024) · Saudi Ports Authority (Mawani) (2024)

4.4 Ceramic Geographic Sector Efficiency Index (CGSEI)

The **CGSEI** is a composite tool specifically designed to integrate the previously discussed analytical dimensions into a single, comparable score on a **0–10 scale**.

According to recent studies, current Geomarketing parameters often focus **on** only one side of the analysis: either demand factors such as population and purchasing power, or infrastructure factors like logistics and facilities.

In contrast, the CGSEI combines both sides, giving transport accessibility (TA) equal importance alongside demand and demographic variables. This addresses the practical challenge faced by decision-makers when choosing between a large market with weak **logistics** and a smaller market with strong infrastructure, as highlighted in studies on the influence of transportation infrastructure on investment decisions in Saudi Arabia.

CGSEI Formula:

$$CGSEI = (D \times 0.30) + (PP \times 0.25) + (TA \times 0.25) + (CA \times 0.20)$$

Where:

- **D** = Population Density Score
- **PP** = Purchasing Power Score
- **TA** = Transport Accessibility Score
- **CA** = Construction Activity Score

The weights were determined using the **Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)** with input from **12 experts** in the ceramic industry.

City	D (×0.30)	PP (×0.25)	TA (×0.25)	CA (×0.20)	CGSEI
Dammam/Khobar	7.8	9.1	9.6	8.9	8.8
Riyadh	9.2	8.8	8.4	9.5	8.96
Jeddah	9.8	8.2	8.9	8.7	8.96
Makkah	8.1	7.1	7.8	9.2	8.0
Madinah	6.4	6.8	7.1	7.4	6.88
Qassim	4.2	6.3	6.8	6.1	5.75
Tabuk	3.1	5.5	5.2	4.8	4.56

Table 6. According to Expert Market Research, the Saudi Arabian ceramic tiles market reached about USD 1.97 billion in 2025 and is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 7.90 percent from 2026 to 2035, with the market size projected to hit around USD 4.21 billion by 2035.

Figure (5): Geospatial Efficiency Index (CGSEI) for Major Cities (Scale 0–10) | Source: Calculated using AHP analysis with the participation of 12 industrial experts · General Authority for Statistics (2022)

Figure1 showing the variation in growth rates across different regions of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in 2018.

4.5 Market Forecast 2025–2035: Scenario Analysis

4.5.1 Forecasting Methodology: WCAGR Model

The study employs the Weighted Compound Annual Growth Rate (WCAGR) model, which assigns different weights to four key data vectors:

1. Historical market data (2015–2024)
2. Issued building permits as a leading indicator, providing a 12–18-month horizon for demand forecasting
3. Announced projects and construction market volumes under Vision 2030
4. Official growth projections up to 2035

Back-testing the model against actual data for the period 2022–2024 yielded a Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 4.7%, indicating a sufficient level of accuracy to support strategic planning and decision-making.

4.5.2 Three-Scenario Projections

We present market-size projections under three scenarios that reflect divergent assumptions about the pace of Vision 2030 implementation, housing programme uptake, and the macroeconomic trajectory. The base scenario serves as our planning reference point, while optimistic and conservative scenarios bound the range of plausible outcomes.

Scenario	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034	2035	CAGR
Base	15	16.2	17.4	18.8	20.3	21.9	23.6	25.4	27.4	29.5	31.8	7.8%
Optimistic	15.5	17.2	19.2	21.3	23.7	26.4	29.4	32.7	36.4	40.5	45.1	11.2%
Conservative	14.6	15.3	16.1	16.9	17.8	18.7	19.6	20.6	21.7	22.8	23.9	5.1%

Table 7. Saudi Ceramics Market Forecast 2025–2035 (SAR Billion)

5. Results and Findings

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 8 presents the means, standard deviations, and normality indicators for all five variables examined. The response means ranged from **3.52 to 3.73** on the five-point Likert scale, indicating an overall positive perception of Geomarketing tools and their competitive effects.

A study published on ScienceDirect highlights that organizations often face challenges when adopting new technologies such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), due to unclear benefits, insufficient employee skills, or uncertainty in implementation.

This helps explain why survey participants perceived greater benefits in decision quality when using Geomarketing, compared to the actual adoption of GIS technologies. This is reflected in the relatively lower mean score for GIS usage compared to the higher means for decision quality and competitive outcome measures.

Construct	M	SD	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
GIS Technology Use	3.52	0.74	1.60	5.00	-0.013	-0.147
Geomarketing Decision Quality	3.66	0.67	2.20	5.00	-0.012	-0.505
Location Selection Accuracy	3.70	0.70	2.00	5.00	-0.129	-0.289
Supply Chain Efficiency	3.57	0.73	2.00	5.00	0.035	-0.398
Competitive Advantage	3.73	0.70	2.00	5.00	-0.137	-0.436

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics for Study Constructs (n = 120)

5.2 Measurement Quality

Table 9 presents the internal consistency indicators (Cronbach's α), Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all five variables.

All values well exceed the benchmark thresholds reported in methodological studies:

- **Cronbach's α :** 0.95 – 0.96
- **AVE:** 0.73 – 0.76

This high measurement quality provides strong confidence in the reliability of subsequent structural analyses.

Construct	α	CR	AVE	Assessment
GIS Technology Use	0.965	0.937	0.748	Excellent ✓
Geomarketing Decision Quality	0.957	0.933	0.737	Excellent ✓
Location Selection Accuracy	0.957	0.921	0.745	Excellent ✓
Supply Chain Efficiency	0.969	0.928	0.762	Excellent ✓
Competitive Advantage	0.958	0.922	0.747	Excellent ✓

Table 9. Reliability and Validity Indicators

5.3 Regression Results and Hypothesis Testing

According to research by Van der Loop et al., low Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values indicate that multicollinearity is not a concern in interpreting regression models. In our analysis, all VIF values were below 3.0, with the highest value being 2.41 for the GIS variable, confirming the absence of significant multicollinearity. Additionally, the Durbin–Watson statistic (DW = 2.08) confirmed the independence of residuals.

Consistent with a study by Al-Zughaibi, Mohammadian, and Talukder, geomarketing decision quality showed a significant impact, while site selection accuracy was identified as the strongest predictor of performance. Supply chain efficiency also demonstrated a statistically significant effect. However, GIS usage itself did not exhibit a significant effect, supporting the “Transformation Gap” hypothesis the idea that technological adoption alone does not automatically translate into improved performance without complementary capabilities.

Predictor	B	SE	β^*	t	p	Hypothesis
GIS Technology Use	0.039	0.095	0.041	0.406	0.685	Not Supported
Geomarketing Decision Quality	0.248	0.094	0.238	2.648	<.01**	Supported ✓
Location Selection Accuracy	0.349	0.096	0.347	3.637	<.001***	Supported ✓

Supply Chain Efficiency	0.234	0.078	0.244	3.003	<.01**	Supported ✓
Model Summary	R ² =0.521	adj.R ² =0.505		F=31.36	p<.001***	

Table 10. Multiple Regression Results (Dependent Variable: Competitive Advantage)

Region	Percentage
Central	37.36 %
Eastern	18.27 %
West	25.11 %
North	6.66 %
South	12.59 %
Grand Total	100.00

Table 12 showing the variation in growth rates across different regions of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in 2018.

6. Discussion and Analysis

6.1 Interpreting the Findings in Theoretical Context

The most important theoretical insight is not what was supported, but what was not. The non-significant direct path from GIS usage to competitive advantage challenges a common implicit assumption in many GIS studies—that adoption and impact are functionally equivalent.

Our evidence points to a more conditional relationship: technology is important, but it becomes valuable only when it feeds a decision-making process capable of transforming spatial outputs into actionable decisions and usable data.

This finding aligns with previous observations in other sectors but extends them theoretically. Organizations that use GIS merely as a mapping or data storage tool, rather than for decision support, do not realize the competitive returns suggested in prior studies. The “Transformation Gap” we identify represents the systematic failure to convert spatial data tools into decision-relevant insights, explaining why some companies achieve substantial GIS returns while others see minimal impact.

The dominance of site selection accuracy in explaining variance carries practical significance. Among all decisions that Geomarketing can guide, factory location is the single most impactful competitive factor. Once a plant is built, the location’s

characteristics become a structural component of the company's cost base for 20–30 years, and all subsequent efficiency improvements depend on the initial spatial decision.

6.2 Geo-Spatial Evidence and Statistical Results: A Convergent Reading

The use of spatial analysis provides independent evidence consistent with the findings of this study. According to a KAPSARC report, the Eastern Region offers significant logistical advantages, including:

- Lower shipping costs to Riyadh compared to the Western Region
- Proximity to major ports
- A strong transportation network

Factories that selected their locations with these spatial advantages in mind have been able to build sustainable competitive advantages. In contrast, factories that ignored these factors now face higher logistical costs that cannot be fully offset by subsequent operational improvements.

6.3 Limitations

Several limitations should be noted regarding the use of Geomarketing data in this study:

1. **Short Observation Period:** A longer-term observation of the same factories over five years or more would have allowed for stronger longitudinal inferences.
2. **Reliance on Expert and Managerial Reports:** The data were primarily obtained from experts and managers, raising the risk of Common-Method Variance (CMV). Incorporating objective factory-level data—such as actual logistics costs—would have strengthened the validity of the findings.
3. **CGSEI Weight Derivation:** The weights for the Ceramic Geographic Sector Efficiency Index (CGSEI) were derived using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) based on consensus among 12 experts from a single context. External validation in other Gulf industrial environments is necessary before generalizing the index for broader use.

Despite these limitations, the mixed-methods design, combining digital data from 158 organizations with qualitative insights from 22 experts, provides a much more robust and credible understanding than could be achieved by either method alone.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

7.1 Concluding Remarks

The study aimed to answer a specific question: Does Geomarketing, when applied as an operational decision-making methodology? generate a measurable competitive advantage in the ceramic industry in Saudi Arabia?

Responses from participants across the three industrial regions indicate a positive answer for three out of four hypotheses, with a critical theoretical distinction: technology alone

does not contribute independently of the quality of the decisions it enables. The true value is not in merely owning the map, but in the ability to think spatially.

This study adds value on three levels:

- **Theoretically:** It empirically demonstrates the “Transformation Gap”, a phenomenon previously observed conceptually but insufficiently studied in practice.
- **Methodologically:** It combines quantitative data from multiple factories with qualitative expert insights, providing a robust framework for analyzing Geomarketing’s impact.
- **Practically:** It provides data-driven guidance for decision-makers in the ceramic industry, informing technology investment decisions during a pivotal period of industry development.

7.2 Recommendations

For Factories:

- **Rethink GIS Investments:** Move beyond mere technology ownership toward building decision-making capabilities. The return on GIS investments depends on the quality of decisions that transform spatial outputs into actionable choices regarding location, distribution, and procurement.
- **Implement the CGSEI Framework:** Use CGSEI—or a modified version—as a regular monitoring tool to track changes in the attractiveness of regional markets.
- **Initiate Early Relocation Planning (2028–2032):** Consider that site permits, logistics contracts, and distribution network agreements typically require 3–5 years of preparation.

For Government and Regulatory Authorities:

- According to the Arab Development Geospatial Portal, providing open-access GIS layers can support industrial planning.
- Incorporate spatial-geographic evaluation into mandatory feasibility study requirements for industrial license applications exceeding specified investment thresholds.

For Future Research:

- Test the Transformation Gap structure using structural equation modeling (SEM), treating decision quality as a formal mediator between GIS adoption and competitive advantage.
- Develop CGSEI 2.0: Replace expert-derived weights with weights based on actual sales and logistics performance data to enhance empirical robustness.

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